

A METHODOLOGY FOR SINGLE AND DOUBLE-LEAK LOCATION IN PRESSURISED WATER DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS USING FLOWRATE-DEPENDENT PRESSURE RESIDUALS VECTORS

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Abstract

Water loss has increasingly become a major concern for water utilities. Loss reduction leads to minimising intermittency and improving coverage in utilities suffering from water scarcity, improving the utility's sustainability, and decreasing operational costs, infrastructure life-cycle costs and risk levels as part of assets management plans.

However, localising leaks is a complex task. On the one hand, although the reactive strategy of repairing leaks when they become visible is needed, most of the leaked water remains invisible. In consequence, Non-Revenue-Water values could be persistently rising and hard to reduce. On the other hand, utilities that have implemented a proactive strategy still face the challenge of selecting an appropriate network of a limited number of conveniently-placed sensors. Unfortunately, enough and well-located instrumentation is only one part of leak location; the other part involves the proper use of data to obtain information that eases the pinpointing activities. In this regard, extensive research has been done using different approaches, such as the use of inverse models [1], pressure residuals [2-4], and inverse transient [5, 6].

This study proposes an approach to the leak location problem by combining analytic and data-based approaches, resulting in a physically-based machine-learning procedure. It involves a representative hydraulic model of a water distribution network (WDN) as a basis for pressure sensitivity analysis and classification algorithms to identify a likely leaking area. A hydraulic model is used to obtain pressure data from the non-leak scenario. Then, individual leaks are placed in all nodes, one at a time, varying the leak flow rate. Later, pressure residual vectors are calculated at the sensor nodes as the difference between the leak and non-leak scenarios. Finally, a classification algorithm identifies the most likely leaking area.

This methodology is applied to the case study of Brăila, Romania. A District Metered Area (DMA) containing approximately 24.6 km pipes, multiple inlets, and eight pressure sensors has been selected within the NAIADES Project for this purpose. Single leaks between 0.05 and 0.5 L/s had a prediction accuracy of 30%, while leaks exceeding 10 L/s were accurately found above 95% of the time.

Overall, it can be concluded that the presented approach has a good potential for locating leaks in WDN of various types; moreover, it is an initial step toward multiple leak location. Finally, recommendations for its use are given, and potential further improvements are outlined.

Keywords: Machine learning, Model-based methods, Leak location, Pressure residuals, Water distribution networks.

1 INTRODUCTION

The sixth of the 17 goals in the Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted by the United Nations in 2015 aims to ensure water and sanitation availability and sustainable management for the world population by 2030. This goal represents a big challenge as by 2021 one in every four people lived in areas subject to water stress, and by 2030 the world is expected to face a water deficit of 40% [7]. This situation implies an urgent call for a more effective and efficient way to manage water in all related sectors, and urban water is not an exception.

Many water distribution networks report enormous water losses levels, as the case of water utilities in Montenegro (68%), Nigeria (62%), Fiji (49%), and Bosnia and Herzegovina (45%), to name a few examples included in the International Benchmarking Network for Water and Sanitation Utilities [8]. Technical losses can occur due to many reasons, such as ageing infrastructure, high water pressure, construction-related problems or inconvenient operation [9]. What makes leak reduction the most challenging is that only a tiny proportion of leaks are visible, while a substantial amount of water infiltrates the ground. Therefore, multiple techniques for leakage estimating, location, and detection are needed.

Water loss reduction has gained an essential role within water utilities. On the one hand, drinking water supply implies operative costs that may be proportional to the water lost, such as supplies for treatment, energy for transportation, and exploitation costs [9]. Leakage can also eventually affect nearby infrastructure, representing maintenance or acquisition additional expenses. On the other hand, leaks negatively impact the pressure of a water supply system and, consequently, the service level and customer perception, not to mention the potential health risk due to pathogen agents or pollution infiltration under service interruptions [9]. Additionally, and especially for water distribution networks (WDN) affected by water scarcity, water losses can make a difference in intermittency and coverage indicators.

Extensive research has been made not only to detect anomalies that aware the water utilities of the existence of leaks but also to locate those leaks and repair them [10-14]. Some approaches that depend mainly on field measurements can take a long time to find a leak, as in night-flow analysis or a detailed search with acoustic equipment. As the volume of water lost directly relates to the time between the leak appearance and its repair, different techniques have been proposed to gain time on leak location.

Data-driven approaches have become more common in this matter; nevertheless, in many cases, the particularities of the physical system are not considered, and only big data mining is used [13, 15]. Mathematical physically-based models and real-time data have been increasingly incorporated into data-driven approaches [16]. However, sometimes these models are used purely to simulate scenarios and obtain synthetic records that the data-driven model will use, without further feedback from the real water network to assist the machine learning model or assess its results.

Model-based analysis complementing data-driven approaches has been broadly used for leak location. Unlike pure data-driven methods, these methodologies do require further knowledge of the real system. For this purpose, they use a hydraulic model of a WDN to calculate steady-state results that will serve as a basis for the following steps. Research in this field has mainly focused on locating single leaks [2-4, 17-20], so further steps should be taken to locate multiple leaks. Moreover, in general, the prediction performance has been assessed for specific flow rates without explicit analysis of the impact of the leak magnitude on the prediction accuracy [17, 18, 20, 21]. In this regard, this study aims to perform an exhaustive and systematic analysis of a wide range of leaks in the complete model to understand the underlying factors impacting the leak location performance. At the same time, it intends to open a window of opportunity toward multiple leak location using physically-based machine-learning approaches.

This document is organised as follows: the second section describes the use of pressure residuals in leak location, mentioning previous works and identifying gaps. Section 3 presents the case study to which the proposed approach has been applied. Then, in Section 4, an overview of the methodology for single leaks is given as an initial step to locating multiple simultaneous leaks. Next, in Section 5, the results obtained from its application to the case study are reported. Finally, the resulting conclusions are presented in Section 6.

2 USE OF PRESSURE RESIDUALS FOR LEAK LOCATION

The pressure at a certain point in a WDN is determined by the available head at the supply source and the energy variations throughout the system. Besides specific elements such as pumps and pressure control valves incorporating or reducing energy to the flow, the friction between the water and the infrastructure assets derives energy losses. The friction losses increase proportionally to the square of the velocity of the flow; consequently, a leak, modelled as an additional demand, causes a drop in pressure at the nodes. The difference between the scenario without leaks and the scenario with leaks is called a pressure residual [2]. Any deviation from the expected pressure values for a certain time infers a larger demand and potentially a leak.

The effect of leaks on a set of reference nodes has been studied using a sensitivity matrix [1]. The sensitivity matrix S contains the pressure variation in a reference node M due to a leak from an orifice of an area A in node J , as shown in Equation 1. The columns in the matrix are called residual vectors.

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial p_1}{\partial A_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial p_1}{\partial A_J} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial p_M}{\partial A_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial p_M}{\partial A_J} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

With their work, Perez, et al. [2] gave rise to further research on pressure residuals to locate leaks. They based their methodology on Pudar and Liggett [1] and proposed a binarised sensitivity matrix considering a pressure drop threshold. Residual values higher than the threshold mean that the considered leak affects the correspondent sensor node and obtains a value of 1. The authors acknowledged that selecting the threshold was a determinant for the process. Later on, it was stated that the binarisation process implies a certain loss of information [3, 22]. Quevedo, et al. [3] used the complete sensitivity matrix and employed the correlation function between the observed residual vector and the individual vectors in the matrix to assess the similarity and predict the leaking node.

Casillas, et al. [17] replicated the normalised sensitivity matrix concept. They applied five methods for leak location prediction: binarisation, Euclidian distance, correlation, angle comparison and least square optimisation; the best results were obtained with the latter two. However, it was not evaluated whether the proposed sensitivity matrix changes for different leak flowrates. Based on Pérez and Quevedo, Meseguer, et al. [23] proposed a decision support system for online leaks location, using the correlation coefficient as a prediction element. The correlation coefficients were obtained using a sensitivity matrix and a pressure residual vector derived for the same leak flowrate, implying that the leak size must be estimated first. Therefore, it cannot be known how the methodology would have performed if the leak flowrate were completely unknown, as it usually is.

Candelieri, et al. [4] developed two case studies in Italy and Romania, simulating scenarios with one leak only in each case, varying the flowrate. They used spectral clustering algorithms (K-means, farthest-first and Partitioning Around Medoids) and not-network-based clustering algorithms (K-means and farthest-first) to group similar residual vectors. In order to assess the

quality of the clustering process, they used a previously proposed measure called the "Localisation index" [24]. After successfully clustering the pressure and flow variation sets, they used SVM to relate a new data set from field measurements with a leaking cluster. The authors conclude that spectral clustering is highly efficient but computationally demanding; thus, it may be not highly efficient for large-scale problems.

Soldevila, et al. [25] recognised that pressure residual vectors for many nodes could be very similar and, therefore, indistinguishable. To solve this issue, they proposed to group nodes with similar signatures in a composed class before using the K-Nearest Neighbours algorithm for classification purposes. A 24-hour extended period was employed in the analysis, demonstrating higher prediction accuracy when the time horizon was larger. One benchmarking network and two real cases were used to assess the methodology.

Previous research on leak location using pressure residuals has contemplated high leak flow rates [18, 19]. In many cases, the assessment of the prediction is done over the complete test data set without further detail on the relation between the accuracy and the leak magnitude [2, 17, 18, 20, 21]. Although there is no specific flowrate threshold differentiating the hidden and visible leaks, the higher the flow rate, the more likely the leak will be visible; thus, a location analysis may no longer be needed. In this regard, leak location methodologies should be analysed for a large range of flow rates to ensure their support to the water utility to locate hidden leaks. That is to say, it is necessary to analyse the resulting accuracy for a vast range of leak flow rates.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Hydraulic model simplification and update

This stage has two main objectives. The first is to update and calibrate the model, considering that the first step in a model-based analysis is to obtain an accurate representation of the real system. The second objective is to reduce the search space by simplifying the model. A model is a reduced representation of reality by definition; nonetheless, it may still imply a wide search space that could create inefficiencies during the training data generation and leak location stages and affect the accuracy of the leak location.

For this matter, several activities shall be carried out:

- *Preliminary review and field validation*

First of all, a reconnaissance of the model must be made. It refers to an understanding of the water sources, the network's connectivity, the demand nodes, the function, placement and operational status of valves, consumption patterns, placement of sensors, and the material, roughness and size of the pipes.

The following aspects must be carefully reviewed and, if possible, field verifications should be carried out: similarity between the model and the base information contained in the GIS or network blueprints, nodes in close proximity that can be irrelevant for hydraulic purposes, connectivity of crossing pipes, disconnected nodes in the hydraulic model, dead-end nodes that may be connected to nearby pipes, nodes that are drawn over a pipe but not connected to it, and duplicated pipes resulting from errors during the GIS drawing process.

- *Model simplification*

Each modelling software has its way of representing elements from a water network. The conversion process from one software to the other implies the creation of auxiliary nodes to establish the precise location of elements such as pumps and valves. However, those auxiliary nodes are hydraulically irrelevant to the model, but they enlarge the size of the sample space, increasing the computational time of the algorithms when simulating and locating leaks.

Three types of elements are removed to simplify the model: first, auxiliary nodes with no consumption; second, nodes joining two pipes with the same diameter and roughness, with no consumption assigned; and third, valves included as independent elements (a closed valve can be represented by a closed pipe without enlarging the model).

- *Assignment of boundary conditions*

The proper boundary conditions for the model must be acknowledged. The most common case relates to the available head at the supply nodes, which is measured in the field and then included in the model.

- *Calibration*

Calibration comprises two aspects. The first is related to the roughness of the pipes, which can be represented by the Hazen-Williams equation's C coefficient or the Darcy-Weisbach equation's k value. Roughness calibration is formulated as an optimisation problem where RMSE between the observed and the simulated pressure values is to be minimised, following Equation 2 [26].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize RMSE} &= \frac{1}{S * T} \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T (P_{obs} - P_{sim})^2 \\ P_{sim} &= f(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where S is the number of sensors, T is the number of time steps included in the simulation, P_{obs} refers to the pressure observed or measured in the sensors, and P_{sim} refers to the simulated pressure results. The simulated pressure values are a function of the roughness coefficients $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, whose values are allowed to vary within a pre-determined interval in the optimisation process.

The second calibration aspect is related to the mass balance and refers to the representation of the existing leakage. It is approached by using a genetic algorithm to include emitter coefficients to specific nodes in order to simulate current leaks, the sum of difference squares, as shown in Equation 3 [27].

$$\text{minimize} \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{NH} w_{nh} \left(\frac{H_{sim} - H_{obs}}{H_{pnt}} \right)^2 + \sum_{n=1}^{NQ} w_{nq} \left(\frac{Q_{sim} - Q_{obs}}{Q_{pnt}} \right)^2}{NH + NQ} \quad (3)$$

Where NH and NQ are the number of observed hydraulic grades and discharges, respectively; w_{NH} and w_{NQ} are normalised weighting factors for observed hydraulic grades and discharges; H_{sim} and Q_{sim} are the simulated hydraulic grades and discharges; H_{obs} and Q_{obs} are the observed values for both variables; H_{pnt} represents the hydraulic head per fitness point and Q_{pnt} the discharge per fitness point, which are used to weight the evaluation of flow and hydraulic head. The constraints of the optimisation problem are the minimum and maximum values for the emitter coefficients and the number of nodes that the algorithm can assume to be leaking.

- *Disaggregation of total demand*

The total demand of a WDN is composed of consumption and leakage. The consumption includes regular households and large customers that may be residential or non-residential, as shown in Equation 4.

$$D = C_{HH} + C_{LC} + L \quad (4)$$

Where D is the total demand, C_{HH} represents the household consumption, C_{LC} the water used by large clients, and L represents the leakage, all in discharge units.

While the monthly consumption of households is commonly measured, their daily usage pattern is usually unknown. For this reason, the overall demand is usually assigned to the nodes; however, considering that the total demand contains consumption and leaks, it is inaccurate to assume the consumption curve to be equal to the demand curve. Hence, the leakage must be estimated to isolate the consumption from the total demand. The difference between the total demand and the predicted night consumption at the minimum night flow (MNF) hour is used to compute leakage. By knowing the pressure at each time step, the FAVAD equation [28](see Equation 5) allows estimating the leakage for all times t .

$$L_1 = L_0 \left(\frac{P_1}{P_0} \right)^{N_1} \quad (5)$$

Where P_0 is the initial average zone pressure at MNF hour, P_1 is the average zone pressure at other time t , L_0 is the initial leak flow rate at pressure P_0 , L_1 is the leak flow rate at pressure P_1 , and N_1 is the leakage exponent. N_1 can go up to 1.5 for plastic pipes or down to 0.5 for rigid pipes, according to Lambert [29]. The author recommends to "assume a linear relationship ($N_1 = 1.0$) in absence of knowledge of pipe materials and leakage level". Finally, the resulting consumption pattern is assigned to the nodes of the model.

3.2 Training data generation process

The first step to calculating the pressure residuals is to run the hydraulic model that represents the current state of the network with no further leaks, denominated *healthy model*. The resulting pressures are stored in a matrix with M columns containing the nodes and T rows representing the timesteps. These results constitute the point of comparison of all leaking scenarios.

Because all nodes in the hydraulic model are possible leak locations, extra demands are placed on each of them for every time slot. When incorporating leaks into the hydraulic model, they must not be added to the existing base demands to avoid them being multiplied by the consumption curve. Then, the model is run one more time, and the pressure values in the sensor nodes are read. All residual vectors are stored for every hour, so the total number of vectors is the product of the number of leak nodes and the leak values.

The Python library WNTR [30] is used for all simulations and data gathering purposes. WNTR is based on Epanet and is compatible with versions 2.00.12 and 2.2. It allows the user to simulate hydraulics and water quality from an existing model, modify features, create a new model from scratch, perform changes in the network operation, add disruptive incidents, and evaluate response strategies. Pressure-driven analysis is used in the study, as opposed to most of the referenced works, which rely on demand driven analysis.

3.3 Leaks location approach

The leak location problem has been considered a multiclass classification problem. The machine learning (ML) model inputs are the residual vectors, and the outputs are the IDs of the leaking nodes. When a leak is detected due to a fall in pressure, the sensor nodes are monitored. The residual vector corresponding to the actual leak is derived by comparing the pressure measurements to the values from the healthy system. Then, the leak's residual vector is compared to the training data and classified as a match to a certain leaking node based on a similarity index.

The leak location approach aims to identify a likely leaking area rather than a single leaking node. The underlying reasons for this decision are two. First, leak management comprises three stages: awareness, location, and pinpointing [10]. The scope of this approach corresponds to leak location, namely, narrowing down the leak to a certain area where pinpointing activities can be effectively and efficiently made. Second, the base assumption for placing leaks as additional

demands is that leaks occur in a node rather than a pipe. Because this is a simplified representation of actual bursts, the forecast of a single node implicitly refers to a larger region.

When comparing the leak's residual vector, namely the *test vector*, with the training data, there is a chance that the most similar training vectors, or points in the multi-dimensional space, correspond to a single node. This condition may be more typical at low leak flow rates when the pressure residuals curves are closer to one another, as shown in Figure 1. In this situation, the leak location process would fall short of its goal. To avoid this problem, it is necessary to guarantee that several nodes are selected to compile a leaking area.

Figure 1. Variation of pressure residuals with the leak flow rate

Several machine learning algorithms were attempted for prediction; however, KNN was selected due to its adaptability to the mentioned physical context of the problem. An additional step was introduced to avoid selecting multiple neighbours corresponding to a single node. The test vector is compared to all elements in the train data set, and a similarity index is computed in each case using Equation 6.

$$S(p, q) = S(q, p) = \frac{1}{1 + d(p, q)} \quad (6)$$

Where S is the similarity index between vectors p and q , and d is the distance between them. For this matter, Euclidian distance (ED) and cosine distance (CD) were used. After repeating the computations for all times t , the average similarity for each residual vector within the training data is obtained. So far, there are (N leaking nodes * F leak flow rates) similarity values, but as a single value for each node is required, only the maximum index remains for each node. At this point, N similarity values are expected, one for each node in the model.

The number of nodes included in the leaking area is denominated k . The greater k , the larger the leaking region is expected to be, and the prediction accuracy is likely to improve. However, wider areas will require larger resources for pinpointing.

Finally, the k nodes with the highest averaged similarity index make up the predicted leaking area. A binary score is assigned according to Equation 7 to assess the prediction accuracy.

$$\phi_{ab} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } a \notin \text{predicted leaking area} \\ 1 & \text{if } a \in \text{predicted leaking area} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Where ϕ_{ab} is the prediction accuracy for a leak occurring in node a with a flow rate b . In this line, a prediction is considered accurate if the actual leaking node is an element of the predicted leaking area, with no regard to the number of nodes contained in it.

The overall accuracy for the complete test data set is evaluated with Equation 8.

$$\Phi = \frac{\sum_{a=1}^n \sum_{b=1}^f \phi_{ab}}{nf} \quad (8)$$

Where Φ is the overall accuracy of the predictions, n is the number of nodes where the leaks are simulated, and f is the number of modelled leaks.

3.4 Testing leakage scenarios

Two experiments are proposed to assess the leak location methodology. The first, *E.01*, considers random leak magnitudes to be placed in all nodes in the model. The second, *E.02*, comprises leak flow rate intervals covering the range included in the train data set without repeating its values.

On the one hand, the random test data set is intended to evaluate the general performance of the leak location methodology; nevertheless, there is no control over whether low and high flow rates are represented. The intervals test data set, on the other hand, is designed to address the difficulties of comparing results and determining the reasons for mispredictions. In addition, experimenting with a wider variety of leak magnitudes evenly distributed across all nodes improves the repeatability of the experiment and allows for a better understanding of the methodology's performance related to the leak size.

4 CASE STUDY

The case study considered in this paper corresponds to one of the three pilots in the NAIADES Project. Brăila county is located in the Muntenia region, eastern Romania, 200 km northeast of Bucharest. The DMA selected for the case study, Radu Negru, is located in the southwestern part of the city. It has a predominantly residential character, with some schools, small local commerce and government institutions. This DMA has multiple inlets, two of which are always operational while the others are turned on and off periodically. The original hydraulic model was simplified and calibrated, containing 144 nodes and 172 pipes that sum up a pipe length of 24.3 km.

Besides the flow and pressure sensors located at the entrances, eight pressure sensors exist in the DMA. They are represented in the EPANET model by nodes named Sensor1 to Sensor4 and PT1 to PT4. The nodes referred to as PT represent large consumers, namely, residential blocks fed by hydrophores. Figure 2 shows the location of the current instrumentation in the DMA.

Figure 2. Sensors placement in Radu Negru's network

This DMA is fed by pumping stations located outside the district's boundaries that supply water to in-between areas. Consequently, the intermediate consumption makes the head boundary conditions at the entrances of Radu Negru highly variable.

For building the training data, 36 leak magnitudes were simulated, from 0.5 to 18 L/s (half or the DMA's daily average demand). Due to the model simplification process, the number of nodes was

reduced from 302 to 144. Accordingly, the training data comprises 5 184 residual vectors for each time t . These vectors also represent points in a multi-dimensional space, where a sensor node determines each dimension. In consequence, the search space in the case of Radu Negru is eight-dimensional.

The testing data used in the proposed experiments are described in Table 1. Both test sets are built without repeating the leaks used in the training set.

Table 1. Test data sets characteristics

Experiment	Leak selection	Leak magnitudes	Test data set size
E.01	Random values	Between 0.5 and 18 L/s	2160 residual vectors
E.02	Leak flow rate intervals	Leaks < 1.0 L/s @ 0.1 L/s 1.0 < leaks < 10.0 L/s @ 0.2 L/s Leaks > 10.0 L/s @ 0.4 L/s	576 vectors per interval, 8 640 in total

5 LEAK LOCATION RESULTS

Previous to running the experiments, the training data were analysed. The correlation between the obtained pressure residuals in all sensors was calculated. If two sensors are perfect-positively correlated, it could be assumed that one of them is redundant and therefore could be left aside, reducing one of the dimensions of the problem. A pairs comparison explained the correlation between them better, showing that even though two of them obtained a high Pearson's correlation coefficient, there are differences that must be considered as they nourish the classification process. From this analysis, it was confirmed that the search space for Radu Negru DMA is eight-dimensional.

5.1 Experiment E.01: random leak values

Two values of k were selected for the node selection, 3 and 5. In addition, two metrics were employed to assess the similarity between the test vectors and the training instances, ED and CD. The prediction accuracy increased with the value of k , as expected (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Accuracy results for E.01 with $k=3$ and 5

Furthermore, in both cases, the results obtained when using CD were better than when ED was used. Suppose a simplification where the variation of the pressure residuals with the leak flow rate is assumed to be linear. In that case, the proportion between the components of a residual vector will remain unchanged for different leak magnitudes. It means that two residual vectors caused by two different leaks will have different magnitudes but the same direction.

Euclidean distance considers the closeness of two multi-dimensional points, while cosine distance computes the angle between them. The two metrics are closely related as two close points (determined that way by computing their ED) may relate to a small angle between them. However, two similar vectors in terms of CD may relate to distant points.

Figure 4. Graphical representation of Euclidian distance and cosine distance

Based on ED, points A and B are more distant than A and C; hence, C would be selected over B as A's nearest neighbour. However, the vectors OA and OC are pointing in different directions. If OA and OC were residual vectors, the ratio between their components would be different, as they may respond to different leak locations. On the contrary, OA and OB have the same direction as they may respond to different leak magnitudes placed in the same location.

Although, in reality, the variation of the pressure residuals is not exactly linear, the change in the ratio between the vectors' components is small enough to use the principle explained before, as confirmed by the obtained accuracy values.

5.2 Experiment E.02: leak flow rate intervals

One remarkable finding relates to leaks placed in certain nodes that did not impact the sensor nodes. This situation was explored throughout all timesteps to verify how the detectability varies with the total demand daily fluctuation. The nodes whose leaks do not produce any impact whatsoever in all sensor nodes throughout all timesteps are designated as *undetectable nodes*. As their residual vectors show no pressure deviation, there is no suspicion of a leak and no point in trying to find it; hence, they were removed from the test data set.

For the first leak flow rate interval, which contemplates leak magnitudes between 0.05 and 0.5 L/s, there were 26 undetectable nodes (18% of the DMA). The next interval comprised 20 nodes, and leak magnitudes over 1.0 L/s were not detected for five nodes. The number of undetectable nodes remains constant for leaks that can be even visible and will not require a pressure-based location methodology to be pinpointed (See Figure 5).

Figure 5. Undetectable nodes for many leak intervals: (a) 0.05 to 0.5 L/s, (b) 0.5 to 1.0 L/s, (c) 16.0 to 18.0 L/s

These five nodes are directly connected to an inlet, so the supply source immediately provides any unexpected demand without causing any effect whatsoever on the sensor nodes. In this regard, any leak occurring in those nodes will not be detected based on pressure residuals calculated with data from the available sensors.

When the performance of the leak location procedure is evaluated as a function of the flow rate variation, the disparities between metrics become more obvious, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Accuracy results for E.02 with $k=3$ and 5

It can be seen how the prediction accuracy changes tremendously as the leak flow rate increases. In the specific case of Radu Negru, the increase in the accuracy is higher below 6 L/s; above this value, the rate of growth is smaller. Leaks over 14 L/s are located 99.3% of the time, while leaks below 2 L/s have a location rate below 42%. According to this, small leaks will require systematic detection and location campaigns that employ different techniques instead of depending purely on pressure data; otherwise, the NRW level will tend to increase over time.

The global accuracy values for the random test data set are similar to those obtained for leak flow rates between 7 and 9 L/s. The prediction accuracy was overestimated for low rates and underestimated for high flow rates when only the random test data set was employed. It is supported by the fact that the leak magnitudes are negatively skewed in the random test data set.

This evidence supports the importance of assessing the leak location methodology on a wide range of leak flows rather than random values or few leak magnitudes.

5.3 General discussion

The accuracy of the proposed leak location methodology and, in general terms, of any leak location methodology should be assessed considering three key factors that clearly influence the results. The first is the leak flow rate. The magnitude of the leak directly impacts the location accuracy. Low leak magnitudes may have a very small or no impact on the sensor nodes as the friction losses they trigger may cause a drop in pressure so small that it falls within the sensors' sensitivity. This situation may occur more often at night when demand is lower, and so is the velocity in the pipes.

Furthermore, the residuals curves are closer to each other for low leak flow rates, and they spread out as the leak magnitude increases. In addition, the closeness of the curves at low flows challenges differentiating one set of curves from another, impacting the accuracy. Oppositely, the more widespread the curves are, the better the distinguishability of the leaking node.

Although it has been proved that the accuracy of leak location is directly related to the magnitude of the leak, it is inappropriate to generalise a threshold for which the prediction results may be considered acceptable. This threshold will depend on several factors specific to each WDN, such as how looped the network is, the diameter of the pipes, the system's demand, and, therefore, the energy losses in the system.

The second factor is the spatial location of the leak. The nodes whose leaks are not detected by the sensor nodes throughout all the timesteps are labelled as undetectable. It was shown that the number of undetectable nodes decreases as the leak magnitude increases; however, some of them remain undetectable even for flows high enough to become visible. No leak occurring in those nodes will be reported based on the pressure residuals, so the water utility will not be aware of any leak occurring in those nodes until it is reported. This situation introduces the third factor, which is related to the location of the sensors. Non-accurate predictions may also be related to the placement of the pressure sensors, as in situations in which they are not able to cover the complete water network. Therefore, it is of utmost importance for a water utility to consider the optimal number of sensors to be used in any DMA or WDN and the optimal instrumentation placement. Large research has been done in this regard [31-35].

On a different note, one advantage of the presented method is that by using a certain value of k , there is adequate control of the extension of the predicted leaking area. However, a drawback has been found. When more than k nodes obtain the same similarity average after all time steps have been evaluated, the algorithm only selects the first k , maintaining the order in which the nodes are read from the hydraulic model. Suppose the actual leak is located in any of the nodes above position k . It will never be accurately predicted in such a case, even if the actual leaking node obtains the same similarity as the predicted ones. In conclusion, the selection criterion in those cases is arbitrary.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents an extended-period approach for locating leaks in WDN based on pressure residuals. This approach is one step toward multiple leaks location. Two criteria to assess the similarity between the residual vector obtained in the presence of a leak and the training data have been used and assessed in the Radu Negru DMA case study (Brăila, Romania). The key messages from this research are listed as follows.

- Three main underlying factors that influence the accuracy of leak location have been identified by testing the presented methodology in a case study. These factors are the leak magnitude, its spatial location and the allocation and coverage of the pressure sensors.
- Although linearity can be assumed to represent the variation of pressure residuals with the leak magnitude, the relation is not completely linear. This behaviour supports the importance of building the sensitivity matrix considering multiple leak magnitudes to construct a robust sample space that can be later used in the leak location methodology. In the same line, a complete assessment of the performance of a leak location methodology must include a wide range of leak flows rather than random values or a limited number of leaks. Similarly, covering the complete network rather than just one or a few nodes in the evaluation helps to reduce bias in the performance assessment.
- The superiority of cosine distance over Euclidian distance when comparing residual vectors was evident in the experiments. The underlying reason is that the ratio among the components of several residual vectors from a certain leaking node tends to be similar for different leak magnitudes. This concept can also be used in future approaches regarding multiple simultaneous leaks.
- This work has taken one step toward multiple leak location, and the proposed methodology can be extended to more than one leak. Although an initial approach has been analysed, a future work is projected to go into further detail on this topic by including strategies to gain efficiency in the search for the leak. Additional node selection criteria to obtain higher prediction accuracy will be assessed as well.

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